

Abstract to ICSE 2025 Artifact Evaluation Track

Artifact Evaluation Track ID: Submission #219

Research Track Paper ID: Submission #1197

Paper Title: EffBT: An Efficient Behavior Tree Reactive Synthesis and Execution Framework

In this paper, we present a novel reactive synthesis method for behavior trees (BTs), namely EffBT, to generate correct and efficient controllers from formal specifications in GR(1) automatically. We implemented it based on the *Spectra*¹ synthesis toolset. Our tool accepts GR(1) formulas as input (described in *.spectra* files), then performs realizability checks. If realizable, it will automatically construct BT controllers that conform to the given specifications. In addition, we integrated a simulation tool that supports running the generated strategies in a random manner, i.e., both the system and the environment will choose their next step arbitrarily.

We are claiming for the “**Available**” and the “**Functional**” badge, since we meticulously prepared our research materials following the ICSE 2025 Artifact Evaluation Track requirements. This includes a pre-configured Docker image, and the regular package along with the installation guide (in case one wishes to install from scratch). In addition, we carefully crafted a *README* file, which provides the introduction to our research artifact, detailed tutorials on how to install and execute our tool, an example for testing the installation, as well as how to reproduce the main experiment results presented in our paper. Finally, we packaged all of these materials into an entirety and uploaded them to the widely-used archival solution website - Zenodo². We believe that our research artifact is worthy of these two badges since they are documented, consistent, complete, exercisable, and include appropriate evidence of verification and validation.

Technology Skills: To configure and use our tool efficiently, we recommend that reviewers know the basic operations of Docker and Linux systems. Furthermore, for a more comprehensive understanding of our tool’s inputs and outputs, we suggest that reviewers familiarize themselves with the basics of BTs and GR(1) synthesis. This information is available in the *Preliminaries* section of our paper, which is also packaged and uploaded to Zenodo.

Artifact Download Site: Our research artifact can be obtained from Zenodo repository ([Download Site](#)). It includes both a packaged docker image that can be run directly and a regular zip file that can be set up from scratch. Along with these, the README file and our paper are also included. Moreover, the regular zip file and the raw experiment results are also available at another *Zenodo Repo* (regular version) ([Download](#) and Unzip the *experimental materials (revised).zip*).

¹<http://smlab.cs.tau.ac.il/syntech/spectra/index.html>

²<https://zenodo.org/>